

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE NATIONAL VETERINARY SERVICE IN THE LIVESTOCK INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *In the scientific article, the Central Asian regions have favorable natural conditions, domestication of current domestic animals from the earliest times, the emergence of animal husbandry and the gradual development of folk veterinary medicine are studied on the basis of spiritual and material historical sources.*

Keywords: *herdsman, domestication, Machay Cave, paintings on the rocks of Sarmishsay, natural self-healing instinct in animals, Konimex, 9 cm tube, Kovuz Tepa, heart valve, surgical surgery.*

INTRODUCTION

People's veterinary medicine in the cattle breeding of Uzbekistan was created in the earliest period of the history of our country with the emergence of farming and animal husbandry. At a certain stage of human historical development, animal husbandry is separated from farming and becomes the main and important branch of economic activity of people, a source of livelihood, creation of material wealth, property acquisition, and the main field of necessary, vital activity. In this process, the types of domesticated animals will gradually increase. Different ways of increasing their productivity, looking, keeping and caring for them, different forms of relations appear. Ways to increase livestock productivity and its effective use are sought.

In the regions of Central Asia with favorable natural conditions, domesticated animals were first trained and domesticated from the earliest times, cattle breeding, horse breeding, and camel breeding developed and became the main factor in the development of society to certain levels, expressed in Chinese annals and other written sources. The first companion of humans was the dog breed.

In the ancient written source, the holy "Avesta", the prophet Spitama addresses the chief god Ahura-Mazda and says, "You created cattle, which are the source of our livelihood." And in the book Yasht (Hymns) of "Avesta", the main deity is the guide to all necessary activities, and when he mentions his 20 sacred names, he gives the following information: "Then Khurmuzd" opened a word in Ahuramaz: "My name is Rakhtya. He describes Sadiq Zaraushtura as a herdsman, a herdsman, a herdsman. This information is based on the fact that the ancient tribes engaged in cattle breeding, the main god Ahura-Mazda created marshy pastures, took the cattle under his protection, even the name "cattle" became the name of the main god, as well as the fact that cattle breeding was one of the foundations of the economic activity of our ancestors even before the appearance of the holy book "Avesta" indicates.

It is no coincidence that in the book "Videvdat" of "Avesta" "where they breed small and large animals, there will be prosperity". Our clan and tribal ancestors who lived in the ancient world were at first engaged in large-scale cattle breeding, goat breeding and small livestock - sheep

and goat breeding. Archaeologist U. Islamov believes that among the ancient monuments in Central Asia, in the territory of Uzbekistan, the archaeological finds in the Machai cave indicate that important economic changes took place among the primitive communities in our country.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Archaeologist M. J. Zhorakulov emphasizes the conclusion that the elements of animal husbandry appeared and developed, i.e., animal husbandry, in the archaeological monuments of the Machai cave, characteristic of the late Mesolithic period, in the actions of ancient hunter-herdsmen. Archaeologist J. Kabirov gives an example of a valuable idea in his work. Our ancestors, who lived in the ancient Zarafshan oasis, may have trained cheetahs and used them to hunt various animals as early as the III-II millennia BC. Because a trained cheetah is better than pure dogs in every way." , - he writes. Of course, if this reasoning is based on the ancient paintings of Sarmishsay on the rocks, then it is not possible to show different periods of historical sources (as if 3-2-1 millennium BC) about the peoples of our ancient land engaged in animal husbandry and turned it into an economic activity includes a long period in its historical development. The pictures of cattle breeding in Sarmishsay testify that they belong to the 3rd-1st millennium BC, and the images of large horned animals belong to the 3rd-2nd millennium BC.

Images of domestic animals on the rocks of Sarmishsay are also found on the rocks of the Karatog, Bukantog, and Morguzor mountains in Central Asia and Azerbaijan. There are more than a hundred ancient monuments that exist in the Suratly stream of the Sokh oasis, in the Zaroutkamar cave of Kohitangtog, in Saymalitoshi of Kyrgyzstan, in the stone gorges of Koybokar, Turgan, Ulugtog, Tomgali in Kazakhstan, in Qobistan of Azerbaijan, and in several other mountainous regions of our republic found in places with pictures on rocks.

The above historical, archeological and written sources testify that our ancient ancestors protected livestock from natural or infectious diseases based on the domestication of several hunting animals. The use of treatment methods, the identification of medicinal-healing plants (these plants or various bodies were used by animals under the influence of natural instinct, which people learned by observing them), and the use of them in the folk medicine method became more and more widespread. With the passage of years, centuries, and eras, such actions have been improved, and the service of veterinary medicine has appeared in animal husbandry. A. Kadirov gives unique examples from a number of sources in his work. "Historical facts show that" external medicine first appeared among animals. It is informed by the fact that there are many examples of self-healing of animals from various diseases in the available literature.

For example, one infected wild rabbit collects spider mites, rubs them on its injured area and recovers. Later, when that spider mite was examined, it was found that it has blood-stopping, calming and healing properties. People of Siberia were looking for and eating the roots of Siberian deer Levzen (reindeer root). Because this plant is medicinal, an extract is prepared from it in medicine. Humans have learned this from horses as well, - it is said in this book. Or one Gibbon (a small, man-like ape) had a sore in his mouth and suffered from a serious illness, he found some medicinal plant in the forest, crushed it, made it into a paste, and applied it to the bleeding place and the sore in his mouth.

RESEARCH RESULTS

So, the monkey-gibbon not only knows the medicinal plant, but also knows the method of making medicine-paste from this plant. It should not be concluded that animals know more about the treatment of veterinary medicine than humans. Because for animals, this state is considered a

natural instinct, a passive action, and it cannot reach the level of human conscious action and scientific knowledge. The self-healing instinct in animals has been observed by humans since ancient times, continuing in livestock species that were hunted by humans and later domesticated. In the process of treatment, they identified and studied the types of medicinal plants used by animals, mastered them and used them in the service of daily medicine. It should also be noted that according to the scientists of the field of physiology and pathology, animals find and eat these medicinal plants due to the need to eat them as a result of feeling the hunger that occurs in their body for medicinal and healing plants. If there is a lack of salt, calcium and potassium in the body of domestic animals, they lie on the saltier ground, and many animals drink more water than they need from reservoirs, lakes and ponds containing sulfur, iron and other microelements indicate that it continues until now in the form of instinct. Because these changes in the animal organism are the result of the effect of the self-healing instinct.

In determining the history of primitive people, clans, tribes, ancient peoples, daily life, spirituality, culture, art, medicine, folk medicine, veterinary service, who lived in the territories of modern Uzbekistan, it is important to use unique, historical sources that have been preserved in the motherland for centuries to this day. The paintings found in more than one place are diverse in their content, features, stylistic directions, era, and structure, and are directly famous in Angara, Lena, Enisei, Baikal, Orti, Amur, Ural, Karelia, Kabistan, Africa's Sahara-Kabir, Spain and Depending on the rock paintings in France, it is characterized by similar aspects and proportions.

The ancient Greek historian Herodotus narrates and writes down a characteristic story about the "use of veterinary medicine" by the Scythian tribes (peoples of Central Asia) in animal husbandry. While narrating the method used by the Scythian tribes in order to obtain milk from tajang (stubborn) cows that did not give milk, "the tribesmen took the small marrow bone of a small animal (sheep or goat) and grinded it well, processed it on both ends, and it is also called munshtuk (fist) They made a smoking instrument, a medical and veterinary instrument - a hollow, thin, unique tube. One end of this tube was wrapped around the cow's udder in a "talisman" and inserted into the channel where milk did not come (the doctor did this quickly, secretly and masterfully), and immediately from the other end of the tube, the "magician" blew hard, opened the milk duct and sent air, and in practice milk began to flow. There is no magic involved in this method, but it is a real practical medicine, and the people of our country still partially use this method.

It can be said that the case presented in this example is the first practical method of veterinary medicine widely used by the people in the animal husbandry of our people since ancient times - cattle and goat breeding were used in parallel, and livestock were used as treatment for each other. A number of European scientists, including Yu.M. Kabishchchanov, B.V. Mirmanov, A.D. Drizdo and others, have described this method of treatment of dairy cows in livestock - "this folk method of animal husbandry arose first of all in Africa and the Middle East, after them spread among other peoples" - they put forward the opinion.

In the village of Kalkanota, on the right bank of the Zarafshan River, Navoi Region, up to the Konimekh canal route, a small mole, 9 centimeters long and 1 centimeter in diameter, found among human bones in one of the fortresses of the Achaemenid period (VI-V centuries BC) - a tube made of sheep's bone - proves the unfoundedness of the above-mentioned scientists' opinion. proved According to experts, this method was used 2500 years ago and even earlier by the herders

who lived in the Zarafshan oasis to practice the practical treatment of "magic" in veterinary medicine.

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Those who knew and were able to practically treat these diseases by giving vaccinations and medicines. This method of treatment is simple, the doctor, knowing for sure that the animal is sick, cuts a certain place and drains the blood, and carefully removes the urine from the ureter in a surgical manner, and treats the sick animal by extracting the accumulated toxic substances. In this way, "magician" totemists, folk healers, treated diseases such as jaundice (also in humans), rabies. Or if there is itching, shedding of hair (wool), sores on the sides of horses (especially horses that pull carts and other loads), or if they swell or fester, those who have been able to diagnose and treat such diseases immediately. This method has been known in our people since ancient times. Such sick people were treated quickly, they fed barley to the horses for 40 days, they cured the sick by taking blood from the edge and vein, rubbing and washing.

In our ancient peoples, the extraction of blood, urine, and the extraction of toxic substances were the first manifestations of surgery in the veterinary service of folk medicine in animal husbandry. Ancient veterinarians knew how to diagnose diseases based on the color of blood, i.e. they considered animals with yellow-red blood to be healthy, if an infected animal, for example, had a cold, its blood was dark red. When the method of bloodletting is necessary for the treatment of diseases of cattle, several parts of the cattle's body, even veins, are cut at the same time. In particular, to treat diseases of large horned cattle, the vein from the ear or the space between the heels of the legs, from the leg vein of sheep-goats, or from the blood vein on the upper lip, the ear of pigs or they operated on a blood vessel in the tail and let out blood. When bitten by some poisonous creatures, they performed the treatment in this way and applied medicine to the operation sites. These operations are performed perfectly using sterilized flat, smooth plastic instruments made of surgical iron, copper, bronze. Doctors have been able to provide obstetric services to animals since ancient times. Those who have achieved surgical removal of the damaged

embryo or fetus. The method of performing such surgical operations on animals by special surgeons is widespread only in Central Asia in general. The center was widely used between the two rivers. Of course, castration in mares was carried out by special persons (only a few people), people who knew medical surgery. They performed surgical operations only in spring and autumn.

CONCLUSION

People's veterinary-medical service, "magical" medicine combined with practical veterinary medicine has been improved and experience has been increasing in people over the centuries. In the process of studying the history of ancient veterinary medicine, all peoples have followed such an objective path of development, and the history of the practice of veterinary medicine, which is characteristic of the peoples of Central Asia, was created before all other peoples. Initially spontaneous - deification, combined medically with the "magical" method. Gradually, with the passage of time, the "magic" method of treatment acquires a religious tone, and the state of natural veterinary treatment acquires a secular practical activity. Such a development will take place in East-Central Asia and Transcaucasia. This process takes a long time, and the creation of centralized states affects the strengthening of the country's strength, material and moral well-being, and defense capabilities. Animal husbandry became the source of livelihood, economic activity and material wealth in the life of ancient peoples and tribes of our country in the ancient world. This is the ancient land of Turan Zamin, the land of veterinary doctors who contributed to the development of animal husbandry by treating not only themselves, but also livestock from various diseases.

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